

Regional News

Lake Alchichica, Mexico. Photo by Javier Alcocer Durandyou

LATIN AMERICAN AND THE CARIBBEAN LIMNOLOGY NETWORK: AN INTEGRATED INITIATIVE TO CONNECT COUNTRIES AND RESEARCHERS

Luciana Gomes Barbosa, Carlos López, Javier Alcocer Durand, Irina Izaguirre, Silvia Echeverria Saenz, Franco Teixeira de Mello, Jeymy Walteros, Gabriela Souza Benegas, Natalia Vargas López, Gerardo Umaña Villalobos, Jorge Jose Garcia Polo, Karen Portilla, Nelson Aranguren, Marcela Matamoros, Esteban Balseiro, Margaret Dix, Carla Fernandez Espinoza and Ernesto Gonzales Rivas.

*Latin American and the Caribbean Limnology Network members

Email: lgomesbarbosa@gmail.com

Introduction and background

Latin America is the cultural cradle of relevant civilizations that were precursors of important fields of modern science. For example, advanced agricultural production techniques, already favored food availability for settlements between 5 and 7 thousand years ago (Turci, 2014). Stretching from Mexico to the *Tierra de Fuego* in Patagonia, Latin American and Caribbean identity is a process under continuous construction (Souza, 2011) permeated by historical elements and political events spanning early colonization between the late Pleistocene and early Holocene periods (Bueno *et al.*, 2013). Such historical complexity gave rise to cultures of high richness and miscegenation in different countries, by maintaining characteristics and historical aspects of native cultures, while generating unique scenarios in constant redefinition.

In this sense, these cultural memories and identities are marked by constant redefinition or temporal layers of meanings (Kosseleck, 2006), extrapolating present experiences. In this scenario of great effervescence, Limnology has developed a perfect connection between historical tradition and current innovation in the many research groups present in the region. Some highlights include theoretical bases for relevant theories such as the functioning and ecology of shallow lakes (Teixeira de Mello *et al.*, 2009, O'Farrell *et al.*, 2011, Izaguirre *et al.*, 2015, Carnevali *et al.*, 2016, Barbosa *et al.*, 2020, Meerhoff *et al.*, 2021), and community ecology, including relevant proposals on phytoplankton functional groups (Kruk *et al.*, 2017), among others. However, the currently high

scientific production and high citation rates can be further stimulated by investing and establishing cooperation between already consolidated groups with those in the initial stages of formation. In this sense, nucleation and training can be great allies, redefining relations between Latin American and Caribbean countries and favoring a more equitable development.

One of the most challenging aspects is to establish connections and bridges between the different countries of Latin America and the Caribbean in a scenario of reduced resources for science and technology, as is currently occurring in Brazil and other nations. Since 2020, this scenario of scarce resources has been aggravated by the global pandemic of COVID-19, driving thousands of people into extreme poverty. On the other hand, science has never been so necessary. In this regard, the digital connection and online scientific actions have broadened horizons and indicated the relevance of network projects in increasing the impact of actions and publications, enabling obtaining resources for research development on common issues such as impacts by anthropogenic actions (*e.g.*, salinization, biotic homogenization, and eutrophication, among others) (Torremorell *et al.*, 2021) and climate change consequences (Attayde *et al.*, 2021).

Mission

The creation of a Latin American and the Caribbean Limnology Network arises from the need to strengthen and favor the development of Limnology in these regions, generating spaces for sharing ideas and projects, as well as functioning as an “umbrella” for researchers, societies, and their members, by promoting the integration and development of regional Limnology as a whole (Fig. 1).

General objectives

- To encourage the development of limnological research in Latin America and the Caribbean, with a special focus on spatial and temporal gradients.
- To promote scientific cooperation in limnology among countries from Latin America and the Caribbean.
- To generate shared databases to stimulate the construction of hypotheses and the generation of analyses at large spatial scales.

Specific objectives

- To promote a unique agenda of events, congresses, and joint actions, and enable the participation of network members in these events.
- To support countries where organized scientific societies do not yet exist, aiming at the preservation of the history of limnology, and the development of the limnologist's career.

Fig. 1. Educational design of Latin American and Caribbean Limnology.

- To promote courses and virtual laboratories in partnership between societies and researchers from different member countries.
- To generate the interchange of postgraduate students between different member countries.
- To encourage and promote young limnologists.
- To promote discussions and foster actions such as publications, concerning common problems associated with environmental conservation, especially in the context of climate change and multiple stressors that currently threaten our inland waters.
- To search, through international articulation, for international funding aimed at fomenting research and actions in Latin America and the Caribbean.

- To promote broad scale projects by involving the many countries of Latin America and the Caribbean.
- To develop protocols aiming to standardize limnological sampling and analyses.

Currently, researchers from 18 countries are part of the Latin America and Caribbean Limnology Network. These include Argentina, Brazil, Bolivia, Colombia, Costa Rica, Cuba, Chile, Ecuador, Guatemala, Honduras, Nicaragua, Panama, Paraguay, Peru, Mexico, Republica Dominicana, Uruguay, and Venezuela. Our objective is to expand the participation of researchers and countries, generate opportunities for young students and contribute to the valorization and growth of Limnology in this region. Fig. 2 illustrates some of the great diversity of freshwater systems in Latin America and the Caribbean.

Fig. 2. A. Yojoa Lake (Honduras); B. Huishue Lake (Chile); C. Amatitlán Lake (Guatemala); D. Laguna Viscacha, Tunari National Park (Bolivia); E. Río Negro at Villa Darwin (Uruguay); F. Alchichica Lake (Mexico); G. La Magdalena River (Colombia); H. RAMSAR La Segua wetland (Ecuador); I. Arroyo Minga Porã (Paraguay); J. Río Cuarto Lake (Costa Rica); K. Laguna Grande Ciervo de los Pantanos (Argentina); L. Rock Pools (Brazil) and N. Clavellinos reservoir (Venezuela).

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NEWS FROM MEMBERS

The second edition of the Encyclopedia of Inland Waters | ScienceDirect, edited by Thomas Mehner and Klement Tockner is out!

Nikolai Aladin, from the Laboratory of Brackish Water Hydrobiology - St. Petersburg Russia, sends us this link to “KURT” - Brine Shrimp & the Aral Sea <https://youtu.be/9cFLzCkYHTs>

Lake Kinneret, Israel. Photo by Tamar Zohary